

Patients' experience of digital applications in self-management rheumatic and musculoskeletal diseases: A systematic review and qualitative meta-analysis protocol

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Introduction

Rheumatic and musculoskeletal diseases (RMDs) comprise diverse conditions that commonly impact the joints, bones, muscles, connective tissues and other organs of the body^(1,2). The diseases cause pain and limit mobility and dexterity, and result in disability in severe cases^(1,2). The RMDs affect over 120 million people in all ages in Europe⁽³⁾. Because of the increase of aging and obese population, number of people suffering the diseases is likely to increase further. The diseases progression is irreversible but it can be slowed; moreover, symptoms could be better managed and patients could reduce the burden of disease-related effects by appropriate strategies. Education, physical activity, activity pacing and self-management including promotion of a healthy lifestyle and weight-reduction are core components of disease management^(4,5). In recent years, healthcare system has increasingly been under pressure because personnel shortage. This has called for additional forms to support traditional care systems. The use of digital applications is a promising mode for delivering self-management strategies including education and exercise for RMDs management^(6,7).

According to WHO recommendation⁽⁸⁾, digital health interventions include apps, video calls, telephone calls, web-based programs, as well as the use of social media platforms. There are synchronous forms of digital health interventions (healthcare professionals and patients interact at the same time such as videoconference, tele-health), asynchronous (mobile health applications, web-based programs) or hybrid ones (a combination of both synchronous and asynchronous). Digital health interventions are increasingly used to support traditional care, improving the efficiency of the healthcare system⁽⁸⁾.

Recent studies have been more frequently reporting benefits of digital programs in self-management of RMDs such as providing training activities with flexible timing and overcoming geographic barriers and lack of healthcare professionals in remote areas^(9–11). Some studies even showed that digital applications were non-inferior to face-to-face interventions regarding improving function and reducing pain intensity^(6,7). Although many studies showed supporting evidences, the optimal use of digital programs has not yet reached. Existing barriers include the need of stable Internet connection and good accessing devices, low technology-readiness, reduced capacity, low digital health literacy levels of patients, etc; in addition, the mismatch between patients' needs/expectation and interventions has been reported^(10–12). Those factors could impact on patients' experiences and influence their motivation, preferences and utility regarding digital health interventions. Therefore, we aim to review qualitative papers to systematically explore musculoskeletal patients' experiences of using digital health interventions and determine factors that facilitate the use of digital interventions among patients with RMDs.

Review question

How do musculoskeletal patients experience digital applications in exercise, education and self-management?

Which factors would influence patients' preferences for the digital programs?

Method

We will conduct a systematic review following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA)⁽¹³⁾ and the critical appraisal tool for systematic reviews that include randomised or non-randomised studies of healthcare interventions, or both (AMSTAR 2)⁽¹⁴⁾. Therefore, the protocol was developed in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis Protocols (PRISMA-P) checklist⁽¹⁵⁾.

Eligibility criteria

Inclusion criteria will be developed following the PICO format: (P) Patients over 18 years-old with osteoarthritis and/or other musculoskeletal diseases; (I) Digital health interventions about exercise and/or education and/or self-management strategy. The interventions can be asynchronous or hybrid (including asynchronous and synchronous sections), such as apps,

other mobile health programs, or web-based program. It might be individual or group services; (C) Not applicable; (O) Studies reporting patients’ perspectives, experiences, acceptances, satisfaction, preferences, workload, benefits on using the digital interventions in exercise and/or education and/or self-management strategy. Type of studies are qualitative studies per se or studies with qualitative data (such as mixed-method studies). We will exclude studies with synchronous digital interventions only such as telephone interventions, synchronous telemedicine, synchronous telerehabilitation, synchronous telecare, etc., and qualitative data from clinicians’ reporting.

Information sources

We will use Medline (via Pubmed), Embase, CINAHL and PsycINFO for searching relevant publications, including academic papers (original articles and reviews) or reports of governments/organizations or conference abstracts. Backward citation of included articles will be employed. We will search from inception to July 2023 and limit to English language.

Search strategy

An initial search term will be developed and conducted in Medline database to verify our selection criteria and proposed search strategy. The result of the initial pilot search will be discussed with another researcher. The key words and index terms will be modified after the initial search and in each database. The search strategy will be adapted accordingly before conducting the literature search in Medline, Embase, CINAHL and PsycINFO. The preliminary search strategy is presented in the table below.

<p>Population (1)</p>	<p>"Osteoarthritis"[Mesh] OR "osteoarthritis"[All Fields] OR "osteoarthritides"[All Fields] OR "arthritis, noninflammatory"[All Fields] OR "degenerative joint disease*"[All Fields] OR "noninflammatory arthritis"[All Fields] OR "osteo-arthritis"[All Fields] OR "osteo-arthrosis"[All Fields] OR "primary osteoarthritis"[All Fields] OR "rheumatoid arthrosis"[All Fields] OR "Arthritis"[Mesh] OR "arthritis"[All Fields] OR "Musculoskeletal Diseases"[Mesh] OR "musculoskeletal disease*"[All Fields] OR "musculoskeletal"[All Fields]</p>
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Intervention (2)	<p>"Digital Technology"[Mesh] OR "digital health"[All Fields] OR ("digital"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields]) OR "digital intervention*"[All Fields] OR "telemedicine"[MeSH Terms] OR "telemedicine"[All Fields] OR "telemedicine"[All Fields] OR "telehealth"[All Fields] OR "tele-health"[All Fields] OR "mhealth*"[All Fields] OR ("mobile"[All Fields] AND "health"[All Fields]) OR "m-health"[All Fields] OR "mobile health"[All Fields] OR "Mobile Applications"[Mesh] OR "mobile application*"[All Fields] OR ("mobile"[All Fields] AND "application*"[All Fields]) OR ("mobile"[All Fields] AND "apps"[All Fields]) OR "mobile apps"[All Fields] OR "apps"[Title/Abstract] OR "Smartphone"[Mesh] OR "smart phone"[All Fields] OR "smartphone"[All Fields] OR "smart-phone"[All Fields] OR "Internet-Based Intervention"[Mesh] OR "webbased"[All Fields] OR "web-based"[All Fields] OR "web based"[All Fields] OR "home-based"[All Fields] OR "internet-based"[All Fields] OR "internet-delivered"[All Fields] OR "online"[All Fields] OR "ipad"[All Fields] OR "iphone*"[All Fields] OR "tablet device"[All Fields] OR "self management"[MeSH Terms] OR "self management"[All Fields] OR ("self"[All Fields] AND "management"[All Fields]) OR "self care"[MeSH Terms] OR ("self"[All Fields] AND "care"[All Fields]) OR "self care"[All Fields]</p>
Type of study (3)	<p>"Qualitative Research"[Mesh] OR ("qualitative"[All Fields] AND "research"[All Fields]) OR "qualitative research"[All Fields] OR "qualitative stud*"[All Fields] OR "Focus Groups"[Mesh] OR "focus group*"[All Fields] OR "Grounded Theory"[Mesh] OR ("grounded"[All Fields] AND "theory"[All Fields]) OR "grounded theory"[All Fields] OR "mixed method"[Title/Abstract] OR "mixed-method"[All Fields] OR "phenomenolog*"[All Fields] OR (("thematic*"[All Fields] OR "thematized"[All Fields]) AND ("analysis"[MeSH Subheading] OR "analysis"[All Fields])) OR "framework analysis"[Title/Abstract]</p>
	<p>#1 AND #2 AND #3 Limit: age>= 18, language: English</p>

Data selection and data extraction

Data selection

Two researchers will select 20% of all studies randomly (called the sample of representative studies) in order to carry out screening titles and abstracts. We will do a pilot stage with the first 10 papers. Consensus meetings will be organized at the threshold of 25%, 50% and 100% of the sample of representative studies in order to achieve a kappa score of 0.8 or greater. Disagreements will be solved by discussion or by the third researcher. The remaining studies will be screened by one researcher.

The full-text of eligible studies will be retrieved and assessed by one researcher, with a second reviewer checking agreement on 20% of the relevant studies by randomization in order to achieve a kappa score of 0.8 at least. A consensus process will be conducted to solve disagreements at thresholds of 25%, 50% and 100% of the checking sample. Disagreement or lack of consensus will be resolved through discussion or by the third researcher.

Data extraction

Data of the full-text of the included articles will be extracted by one researcher; a second researcher will check agreement on a 20% random sample. A consensus process similar to the one described above will be conducted to resolve disagreements. The extracted data includes title, author, year, country, study design, data collection method, participant characteristics, sample size, type and description of the digital intervention, and qualitative information/data (themes/sub-themes, quotes) regarding perspectives, experiences, acceptances, satisfaction, preferences, workload, benefits disclosed in results, discussion (if applicable), or annex/appendix sections.

Risk of bias

The methodological quality will be evaluated by using the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) guidelines⁽¹⁶⁾. Two investigators will conduct it independently. Discrepancies will be solved by discussion or the third investigator will be consulted if necessary.

Data synthesis

The thematic meta-synthesis will be conducted, including following steps: First, a line-by-line coding of primary data will be performed; Then, descriptive themes will be generated from analysis of results of the included studies; Finally, analytic themes will be produced by

analysing each code and merging them based on thematic similarity, in order to create major themes relevant to our aim in this meta-synthesis. A pilot stage of the thematic synthesis will be conducted with expert researchers in qualitative research to create pre-defined codes to help guide the analysis. One researcher will implement line-by-line coding of data extracted from primary studies. When coding will be finalized, a second researcher will check the accuracy of a random sample of the coding (10%). Two researchers will systematize the descriptive and analytic themes. We will specifically consider three aspects including (i) structure (the digital program's features, utilization,...), (ii) process (how patients use it, interactions...) and (iii) outcome (such as benefits from using digital interventions) in Donabedian framework in our analysis. In addition, we will use natural language processing and clustering algorithms to support the qualitative analysis.

Confidence in the evidence

We will use the Confidence in the Evidence from Reviews of Qualitative Research (GRADE-CERQual)⁽¹⁷⁾ approach to assess the level of confidence for our main findings. The method aims to assess the extent to which confidence can be placed in findings from qualitative synthesis. This approach will assess the findings in 4 components: Methodological limitations, Coherence of review findings, Adequacy of data, Relevance of included studies. They will be ranked according to the degree of concerns: "no or very minor concern", "minor concern", "moderate concern", and "serious concern". After that, the overall assessment will be implemented to grade overall body of evidence as "high", "moderate", "low" or "very low" confidence. The findings will be begun as high confidence and then downgraded by one level in confidence if presenting "minor" and "moderate concerns"; if evidences present "serious concerns", two levels in confidence will be downgraded by. Two researchers will complete GRADE-CERQual independently and then discuss to resolve differences.

Conflicts of interest

There is no conflict of interests among authors related to this research to declare.

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